

Evaluation of Correlation between Clinical and Radiological Findings and the Role of Diagnostic Laparoscopy in Chronic Abdominal Pain**Himanshu Kumar Choudhary¹, Sujata Kumari², Subhash Kumar³, Sushma Kumari⁴**¹Assistant Professor, Department of General Surgery, Narayan Medical College and Hospital, Jamuhar, Sasaram, Bihar²Assistant Professor, Department of Anatomy, People's College of Medical Sciences and Research Centre, Bhopal, M.P.³Professor, Department of General Surgery, Narayan Medical College and Hospital, Jamuhar, Sasaram, Bihar⁴Professor and HOD, Department of Pharmacology, Narayan Medical College and Hospital, Jamuhar, Sasaram, Bihar

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Abstract:**Background:** One of the most challenging abdominal disorders to treat is chronic discomfort. Persistent abdominal pain is a challenging complaint. The majority of patients in this group would have already had numerous diagnostic tests performed. Without a doubt, diagnostic laparoscopy serves as a crucial bridge between performing a laparotomy and declining to examine a patient's abdomen. The aim of our study was to evaluate the role of diagnostic laparoscopy in chronic abdominal pain and its correlation with clinical and radiological finding.**Methods:** 48 patients who were admitted to surgical wards participated in our study. The study included all patients with chronic abdominal pain; patients with acute abdominal pain, uncorrectable coagulopathy, uncorrectable hypercapnia, and pregnant women were not included. Detailed history, physical, baseline blood, and radiographic examinations were done to come the diagnosis. Patients underwent diagnostic laparoscopy, and following informed written agreement, the appropriate surgical therapeutic procedures were performed during the procedure in accordance with the etiology. An assessment was conducted on the effectiveness of laparoscopy in validating the diagnosis and providing clinical care for individuals experiencing persistent abdominal pain.**Result:** For both sexes, the prevalence of persistent abdominal discomfort was nearly equal. The age range of 31-40% was observed to have the highest frequency. The most frequent laparoscopic discovery was Koch's abdomen, which was followed by persistent or recurrent appendicitis. Forty-eight patients had a definitive diagnosis made, and 38 individuals had demonstrated pain relief following a diagnostic laparoscopy.**Conclusion:** High diagnostic and therapeutic efficacy can be achieved with diagnostic laparoscopy. Laparoscopy not only helps identify a condition, but it also has the benefit of typically allowing therapeutic intervention to be performed in the same session, saving the need for a follow-up hospital stay or abdominal investigation.**Keywords:** Chronic abdominal pain, Diagnostic laparoscopy, Koch's abdomen.

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Introduction

One of the most challenging abdominal disorders to treat is chronic discomfort. It could not be satisfying for the patient or the treating physician. Persistent abdominal discomfort is a challenging complaint. [1] It results in obvious pain and incapacity, both mental and physical. Low life quality is linked to persistent discomfort in the abdomen. [2]. The surgeon is frequently called when an individual patient's disease reaches the boundaries of feasible non-invasive testing, which

is likely to happen without the extensive testing that is done today. Naturally, there is a great probability of an abdominal investigation that is not therapeutic. Without a doubt, diagnostic laparoscopy serves as a crucial bridge between performing a laparotomy and declining to examine the patient's abdomen. The peritoneal cavity may now be perfectly examined visually with laparoscopy with the help of advancements in optics, which also enable histological diagnosis of

target biopsies under vision. When performed by a skilled surgeon, laparoscopy provides a more comprehensive view of the entire peritoneal cavity than an exploratory laparotomy and is typically just as instructive as the former. Our goal in this study is to assess the utility of laparoscopy in the diagnosis and treatment of patients with persistent abdominal discomfort, and to relate the results with radiological and clinical characteristics. Furthermore, in this group, a negative laparoscopic evaluation may save morbidity and avoid an unnecessary laparotomy.

Material and Methods

The present study was carried out on patients admitted in surgical wards in the Department of Surgery of Narayan Medical College and Hospital, Jamuhar, Sasaram, Bihar from April 2023 to March 2024. All patients having chronic abdominal pain were included in the study. Patients with acute abdominal pain, an uncorrectable coagulopathy or uncorrectable hypercapnia and pregnant females were excluded in this study

A total of 48 patients getting admitted in the surgical wards through SOPD, casualty, and transferred from other departments with a complaint of chronic abdominal pain during the period of study were included in the study. On admission, detailed history and clinical examination were conducted giving emphasis on the duration, site of pain, previous history of any surgery, and other related problems. Baseline investigations such as complete blood count, urinalysis, blood sugar (fasting and post-prandial), blood urea, serum creatinine, liver function test, coagulation profile, serum electrolytes (Na, K, Cl, and Ca), HIV, hepatitis B and C profile, blood grouping, chest X-ray, and electrocardiograph were done. Abdominal radiographs, ultrasonography (USG), skiagrams of spine in all cases, and computed tomography (CT) scan of abdomen in selected cases were done to reach to diagnosis. The data were noted on a predesigned pro forma.

Based on the clinical examinations and imaging studies, patients were subjected to diagnostic laparoscopy and the necessary surgical therapeutic interventions during laparoscopy were employed as per the etiology after taking informed written consent. Biopsy from suspected site (peritoneal lesion, omentum, and mesenteric lymph nodes) and peritoneal fluid for routine microscopy and culture-sensitivity were also taken.

Post-operatively, all patients were kept nil orally for 24–48 h. Patients were monitored with pulse, blood pressure, and temperature charting. Injectable antibiotics and analgesics were used accordingly. Ryle's tube and urinary catheter were

removed depending on the condition. Appropriate treatment was started once the diagnosis was established. Patients were followed up at regular intervals post-discharge after the procedure. Subjective assessment of pain was done by asking the patients, what occurred to their pain, relief, reduced, or no change.

This study included the patients who were admitted to the hospital with a history of chronic abdominal pain with inconclusive clinical examination, laboratory, and imaging studies. The findings and outcomes of laparoscopy were recorded in a master chart and analyzed. Outcome measured which included the overall efficacy of diagnostic laparoscopy in finding a cause of chronic abdominal pain and its correlation with clinical and radiological findings, clinical diagnosis made versus final diagnosis, post-operative complications, and response to pain after procedure.

Result

The peak incidence of chronic abdominal pain was seen in the age group of 31–40 years 14 (29.17%). In our study, youngest patient was 14 years' old and oldest was 65 years' old. The mean age of presentation was 35.95 ± 13.65 years. The incidence of chronic abdominal pain was almost equal in both females 25 (52.1%) and males 23 (47.9%). Mean age of presentation in males was 36.26 ± 13.88 and mean age in females was 35.68 ± 13.71 years.

Abdominal pain was present in all cases 48/48 (100%) as a chief complaint followed by abdominal distension in 17/48 (35.41%), fever in 13/48 (27.08%), and 10 patients (20.08%) presented with nausea and vomiting (6 had nausea alone). Anorexia/weight loss was present in 8/48 (16.67%) of patients. Most of the patients 29 (60.42%) had duration of pain ranging between 7 and 12 months, followed by 3–6 and 13–18 months in 8 (16.67%), 19–24 months in one (2.08%), and >2 years in 2 patients. Average duration of pain was 10.92 ± 5.88 months.

Most of the patients was presented with right lower quadrant pain 19 (39.58%), followed by diffuse pain in 13 (27.08%), periumbilical pain in 7 (14.58%), left lower quadrant pain in 2, right upper quadrant pain in 2, left upper quadrant region pain in 2, and right and left lower quadrant pain in 3 cases. Of 48 cases, 13 (27.08%) had a history of previous surgery and 35 (72.92%) had no history of surgery. All patients who presented with post-operative adhesion had a previous history of surgery [Table 1].

Table 1: Baseline characteristics of the patients

Characters	Value
Age (years), Range (mean)	14-65, (35.95±13.65)
Gender	
• Male	23(47.9)
• Female	25(52.1)
Site of pain	
• Right lower quadrant	19(39.58)
• Left lower quadrant	2(4.17)
• Right upper quadrant	2(4.17)
• Left upper quadrant	2(4.17)
• Periumbilical	7(14.58)
• Diffuse	13(27.08)
Right + left lower quadrant	3(6.25)
• Duration of pain (months), Range (mean)	4-30, (10.92±5.88)
• History of previous abdominal surgery	13(27.08)

All subjects underwent USG, of which 18 (37.5%) showed normal USG findings, 15 (31.25%) had dilated bowel loops and bowel thickening, 6 (12.5%) had ascites, 4 (8.33%) had mesenteric lymphadenopathy, while gaseous distension was seen in 2 (4.17%). Other findings were seen in 3 (6.25%) cases. Of the 18 patients with normal USG findings, 5 had no abnormality detected during diagnostic laparoscopy, while 13 patients had new findings (4 had findings suggestive of Koch's abdomen [Figure 1], 4 of chronic/recurrent appendicitis, 3 of pelvic inflammatory disease (PID), one had findings suggesting post-operative adhesion, and one patient had findings suggestive of chronic hepatitis). Of 30 (62.5%) patients with positive USG findings, 12 (25%) patients had similar findings during laparoscopy, 6 (12.5%) had altogether new findings, while 12 (25%) had new findings in addition to previous findings. USG showed 50% efficacy in diagnosing CAP. In our study, CT of abdo-

men was done in 11 (22.9%) patients. 10 (20.8%) patients showed pathological findings (ascites, mesenteric fat thickening, lymphadenopathy, multi-loculated collection, GB mass, dilated bowel loops, pleural effusion, and bowel thickening) in CT, while one CT was normal. In 5 patients, CT showed change in findings when compared with the findings on USG. CT scan was better to suggest dilatation of gut loops and retroperitoneal/mesenteric lymphadenopathy. Of 48 patients with chronic abdominal pain, 17 had findings suggestive of Koch's abdomen, 11 of chronic/recurrent appendicitis, and 7 of post-operative adhesion. 3 patients had findings suggestive of malignancy (2 had suspicion of GB fossa malignancy [Figure 2] and 1 of colonic cancer), 2 cases of PID, 2 had ovarian cyst, and one showed hepatic scar. 5 patients had no abnormality detected during laparoscopy. Positive finding during diagnostic laparoscopy was seen in 43 (89.6%) patients [Table 2].

Table 2: Distribution of operative findings on diagnostic laparoscopy

Operative finding	Number of patients, n=48 (%)
Abdominal Koch's	17(35.42)
Chronic/recurrent appendicitis	11(22.91)
Post-operative adhesion	7(14.58)
Malignancy	3(6.25)
PID	2(4.17)
Ovarian cyst (endometriosis)	2(4.17)
Chronic hepatitis	1(2.08)
No abnormality detected	5(10.42)

PID: Pelvic inflammatory disease

In 17 cases, biopsy (from tubercle, omentum, mesenteric lymph node, and any suspicious tissue with/without ascitic fluid sampling) was taken, followed by appendectomy (alone/ with adhesiolysis) in 15, adhesiolysis (alone) in 7, ascitic fluid sampling (alone) in 4 cases, and excision of cyst was done in 1 case. In four cases, only diagnostic laparoscopy was done. Of the 15 cases of appendectomy, 11 had findings suggestive of appendiceal pathology during laparoscopy and 4 had no abnor-

mality seen during laparoscopy. 13 of 15 appendix removed had positive pathology histologically. Of 11 biopsies from tubercle, 9 (81.8%) were positive. Omental biopsy came positive for adenocarcinoma in 2 cases, and in one, chronic inflammation was seen. Biopsy of liver scar suggested chronic hepatitis. Mesenteric fat/ lymph node biopsy showed positive result in 2. Of 15 appendices removed, 14 showed positive result, while one was negative. After correlating clinical and radiological findings,

histopathology reports, and findings of diagnostic laparoscopy, abdominal Koch's was the most common diagnosis in our study in 17 (35.42%) patients, followed by chronic/recurrent appendicitis in 14 (29.2%), post-operative adhesion in 7 (14.58%),

malignancy with metastasis in 3 (60.25%), and PID and ovarian cyst in 2 (4.16%) each. Two patients had no abnormality detected during laparoscopy, and histopathology report was also negative [Table 3].

Table 3: Distribution of patients according to final diagnosis

Final diagnosis	Number of patients
Abdominal Koch's	17
Chronic/recurrent appendicitis	14 (11+3)
Post-operative adhesion	7
Malignancy	3
PID	2
Ovarian cyst (endometriosis)	2
Chronic hepatitis	1
No abnormality detected	2

PID: Pelvic inflammatory disease

Only 3 patients had post-operative complications, fever (2) and surgical site infection (1). No major complications were observed.

Complications were managed conservatively, and patients recovered well. Of 48 patients, 3 had dis-

continued follow-up (they were referred for adjuvant therapy). Of remaining 45, 38 (84.4%) patients had shown resolution of pain during follow-up. No change was seen in 7 (15.6%) cases after laparoscopy [Table 4].

Table 4: Pain response after diagnostic laparoscopy

Effect of intervention	Number of patients, n=45 (%)
Resolution (relieved+reduced)	38 (84.4)
No change	7 (15.6)

Figure 1: (a and b): Peritoneal tubercles with ascites (Koch's abdomen)

Figure 2: (a and b) GB fossa malignancy with hepatic metastasis

Discussion

Chronic abdominal pain is among the most challenging and demanding conditions to treat across the whole age spectrum. Clinical symptoms and signs are usually insufficient, ambiguous, and often misleading for a conclusive diagnosis in these patients. After ruling out common diseases by careful investigations, many patients are still undiagnosed and represent a major diagnostic challenge to the surgeon. [3]

The most common organic conditions include intestinal adhesions, [4,5] appendicular, [6] and biliary causes, [7,8] while functional conditions include irritable bowel disease, [9], functional dyspepsia, [10] and various motility disorders. [11] Abdominal wall pain is also common and frequently mistaken for visceral pain. [12,13]

Diagnostic laparoscopy makes it possible for the surgeon to visualize surface anatomy of intra-abdominal organs with greater details better than any other imaging modality. However, laparoscopy has got its own limitations such as non-visualization of deep parenchymal organs, processes of retroperitoneal space, and the inner surface of hollow organs and not allowing the surgeon to palpate the organs. [14]

All patients included in this study had chronic abdominal pain, and they were subjected to laparoscopic evaluation after exclusion of all organic causes of the pain by detailed history, complete clinical examination, laboratory tests, and radiographic evaluations.

The study confirmed that in this difficult patient group, laparoscopy could safely identify abnormal findings and can improve the outcome in a majority of cases. The subjective benefit of laparoscopy for both the operating surgeons and the patient is the definitive answer that if no serious pathology is found intra-abdominally, the placebo effect of laparoscopy may explain at least partly the patient pain relief. [15]

Based on the findings of above study, it is also clear that early diagnostic laparoscopy can prevent the delay in the arrival at a definite diagnosis and institution of appropriate treatment.

The common causes of chronic abdominal pain were abdominal tuberculosis, chronic appendicitis, gynecological pathology, bands, adhesions, and abdominal malignancy in our study. In many developing countries including India, infectious disease such as tuberculosis is a more common cause of chronic abdominal pain than cancer.

In our study, 18 patients had normal USG finding. Of 30 (62.5%) patients with positive USG findings, 12 (25%) patients had similar findings during laparoscopy, 6 (12.5%) had altogether new findings, while 12 (25%) had new findings in addition to previous findings. USG showed 50% efficacy in diagnosing chronic abdominal pain. Thus, diagnostic laparoscopy clearly scores above the imaging studies in picking up tubercles, nodules, minimal ascites, bands, and adhesion.

In our study, abdominal Koch's was the most common finding 17 (35.45%), followed by chronic/recurrent appendicitis 11 (22.91%), and is comparable to the study by Tulaskar et al., [15] Rathod et al., [16] Lal, [17] and Saxena. [18]

In our study, besides laparoscopy and biopsies, therapeutic surgeries were performed laparoscopically in 23 patients. In patients diagnosed as abdominal Koch's and suspected of malignancy, biopsy was taken, while in 15 patients, appendectomy was done. It is comparable to the study by Rathod et al., [16] Chaphekar et al., [19] Saxena, [18] and Chao et al. [20] in his study concluded that diagnostic laparoscopy is worthwhile for patients with chronic right iliac fossa pain and concurrent appendectomy should be considered in young patients with episodic, well localized symptoms associated with systemic malaise.

In the present study, no cases required conversion to laparotomy for therapeutic management. Salky and Edye [21] reported no conversion rates. Raymond et al. [22] in their study of patients with chronic abdominal pain showed no conversion rate to laparotomy. Klingensmith et al. [23] in their study reported no conversion rate.

Of a total of 48 patients of chronic abdominal pain, positive diagnosis was made in 46 (95.83%) patients in our study and is comparable to the study by Arya et al., [24] Karvandeet al., [25] Paajanen et al., [26] and Saxena. [18]

In our study, 38 (84.4%) patients had shown resolution of pain during follow-up after laparoscopy. It is comparable to the study by Kumar et al. [27] and Chaphekar et al. [19]

There were no major laparoscopy or anesthesia-related complications. Most of patients were discharged in a 2–6 days. Morbidity was 6.25% and there was no mortality. Finding no abnormal pathology on laparoscopic exploration is also considered a useful outcome, as this provides reassurance to the patient and avoids further costly investigations and treatment, as this provides reassurance to the patients and avoids further costly investigations and treatment. Thus, this study highlights the positive role of laparoscopy in patients of chronic non-specific abdominal pain.

Conclusion

In many patients presenting with chronic abdominal pain, even battery of investigations fail to confirm any diagnosis. Many patients remain undiagnosed for prolonged periods because conclusive diagnosis largely depends on direct visualization of abdominal viscera, histology, and further evaluation of ascitic fluid, which requires invasive intervention in the form of laparoscopy or laparotomy. A delay results in progression of the underlying disease, prolonged morbidity and complications. It not only results in inevitable emergency abdominal surgery but also is associated with morbidity and mortality. The lack of accurate diagnosis leads to undesirable burden of human sufferings and wastage of resources.

A conclusive diagnosis by direct visualization with the help of laparoscopy along with histology, culture, or ascitic fluid studies is becoming a necessity in the present-day scenario for initiation of treatment in patients of chronic non-specific abdominal pain.

Early diagnosis with the help of laparoscopy allows a prompt treatment to be initiated with advantages for the patients and savings to health-care system. Our study establishes the role of diagnostic laparoscopy as a safe and useful adjunct to other diagnostic modalities in management of chronic abdominal pain.

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